

ZAKAT AND CHARITY AS ESG-ALIGNED LEADING INDICATORS IN MUSLIMPRENEURSHIP: A FRAMEWORK FOR ETHICAL SUCCESS AND SOCIAL IMPACT IN THE ISLAMIC SOCIAL ECONOMY

Rinto Muhammadsyah Azhar¹
Isral Naska²

¹ Centre of Islamic Studies and Civilisation at Charles Sturt University
250 Hume Highway Somerton Victoria 3062 Australia

² Islam and Minangkabau Research Centre at Universitas Muhammadiyah Sumatera Barat
Jln. Pasir Kandang No. 4 Koto Tangah, Padang, 25172 Indonesia

* Corresponding Author (email: razhar@csu.edu.au)

Abstract: *This paper examines how zakat and charity (sadaqah and infaq) can serve as meaningful, measurable indicators of success for Muslimpreneurs, especially those operating within diaspora contexts. Rather than viewing these acts solely as religious duties, the study frames them as essential components of ethical entrepreneurship that align with Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) principles. Drawing on the Muslimpreneurship Competence Development Framework (MCDF), which adapts the European EntreComp model through an Islamic lens, the research proposes SMART (Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, and Time-bound) leading indicators rooted in Qur'anic guidance. These leading indicators aim to assess not only financial performance but also social responsibility and moral alignment. The analysis highlights the relevance of integrating Islamic social finance tools into business evaluation practices, offering a more holistic approach to entrepreneurial success. Ultimately, the study suggests that incorporating zakat and charity into performance metrics strengthens ethical governance and community well-being, reflecting the broader goals of the Islamic Social Economy. This approach may be especially beneficial in addressing the identity and integration challenges faced by Muslim entrepreneurs in non-Muslim majority societies.*

Keywords: *Muslimpreneurship, Islamic Social Economy, ESG, EntreComp, SMART Indicators, Social Impact*

INTRODUCTION

The global Muslim population is projected to grow from currently 1.9 billion to 2.2 billion by 2030 (The Globalist, 2024). If current trend persists, Muslims are projected to make up 26.4% of the world's population of 8.3 billion in 2030, a 23.4% share increase from 2010 (The Globalist, 2024). A significant proportion of this population resides outside of traditional Muslim-majority countries, creating diverse diaspora communities that span Europe, North America, Asia-Pacific including Australia, and parts of Africa (Kramer & Tong, 2024). For the Muslim diaspora,

economic participation through entrepreneurship is a powerful means of achieving socio-economic integration and upward mobility (J. A. Ali, 2020; Basu & Altinay, 2002; Ghoul, 2017).

For Muslim diaspora, especially the ones who is living in the West, navigating life often involves a various interrelation of factors. They may find themselves balancing the traditions of their faith with the demands of modern society, their spiritual beliefs with the practical realities of everyday life, and their unique cultural identity with the pressures to assimilate into their new surroundings (Fleischmann & Phalet, 2018; Jakubowicz et al., 2014; Roose et al., 2023). In diaspora communities, Muslim entrepreneurs navigate a complicated landscape. They must contend with diverse, and sometimes conflicting, worldviews: the modernist drive for progress, postmodernist critiques of absolute truth, and secular values that can often marginalize religious perspectives (J. A. Ali, 2012; Iner & Cufurovic, 2022).

For many, the challenge goes beyond issues of belonging, economic stability, or career aspirations. It is a deeply spiritual and ethical endeavour—finding ways to remain faithful to Islamic principles and teachings while actively engaging with and contributing to a society grounded in different cultural and philosophical values (Yilmaz, 2019). This dilemma becomes particularly acute in entrepreneurship, where success is typically measured in material terms—profits, market share, and growth—often at odds with Islamic principles and teachings that emphasize ethical conduct, social responsibility, and spiritual fulfillment (Olaofe, 2023).

Given these multifaceted challenges, there is a significant need for a competence development framework that harmonizes both economic and spiritual objectives for Muslim diaspora entrepreneurs. Amidst this absence, the Muslimpreneurship Competence Development Framework (MCDF) emerges as a vital model for addressing these tensions. Synthesised from the work of Bacigalupo et al. (2016) on the European Entrepreneurship Competence Framework (EntreComp) and enriched with Islamic principles and teachings, MCDF offers a faith-aligned approach to entrepreneurial competence. It equips Muslim entrepreneurs to thrive in a globalised, competitive marketplace while maintaining alignment with their religious values (Azhar, 2024).

However, the MCDF currently does not have Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, and Time-bound (SMART) leading indicators. SMART leading indicators would facilitate effective measurement and guidance of the MCDF practical implementation.

This study responds to that need by proposing SMART leading indicators grounded in Islamic concepts of zakat and charity (*ṣadaqah* and *infaq*)—core pillars of the Islamic social economy and natural alignments to Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) principles. Anchored in the first four verses of *Surah Al-Mu'minūn*, the proposed indicators extend the MCDF into a more holistic tool that reflects not only competence but also ethical success and social impact. By foregrounding zakat and charity as ESG-aligned dimensions of entrepreneurship, this study reframes success in Muslimpreneurship as the pursuit of *al-falāḥ*—well-being and prosperity in both this world and the Hereafter.

Qur'ānic Interpretation of Success: Al-Mu'minūn 1-4 and Its Relevance to SMART Entrepreneurship Competence Leading Indicators

The emphasis on *Al-Mu'minūn* is pivotal, as this chapter explicitly mentions "success" in its opening verse, marked by the term *aflaha*, meaning "successful" or "prosperous". Verses 1–4 describe specific characteristics of believers, forming a template for entrepreneurial competence informed by Islamic principles and teachings.

This analysis recognises the axiological perspective of interpreting the Qur'ān, highlighting the importance of the language and context of revelation as emphasised by Haleem (2016). The Qur'ān, revealed in Arabic to the Prophet Muhammad Peace be upon him (Pbuh) between 610 and 632 CE, uses classical Arabic as the medium of divine guidance. Qur'ānic verses revealed in Mecca (*Makkiyyah*) and Medina (*Madaniyyah*) reflect distinct thematic focuses. Classical Arabic references, such as *Lisān al-'Arab* by Muhammad ibn Mukarram ibn Alī ibn Ahmad ibn Manzūr al-Ansārī al-Ifrīqī al-Misrī al-Khazrajī (d. 1311 CE) known as al-Manzūr (1990), are indispensable for accurately interpreting the Qur'ān's linguistic richness.

Haleem's modern interpretation is particularly valuable for this study. His approach respects the Qur'ān's intertextuality, contextual relationships, and nuanced meanings while making the text accessible to contemporary readers. Haleem's avoidance of archaisms and cultural markers ensures clarity, enabling readers to connect Qur'ānic principles with contemporary concepts such as entrepreneurship competence successful attainment (Haleem, 2016).

To ensure theological rigour and linguistic precision, this study also draws on classical exegesis by Abū Ja'far Muḥammad ibn Jarīr ibn Yazīd al-Ṭabarī known as Al-Tabari (d. 932 CE) and the influential interpretations of Abū al-A'lā al-Mawdūdī (d. 1979) known as al-Mawdūdī . Al-Tabari provides foundational insights into linguistic and historical contexts, focusing on the authentic meanings of Qur'ānic terms. Al-Mawdūdī with his modernist approach to Qur'ānic interpretation, links the attributes of a believer to an entrepreneurial mindset. His interpretation offers a synthesis of traditional Islamic values with contemporary, practical applications for modern society. These are complemented by Haleem's emphasis on contemporary relevance, making the study applicable to modern entrepreneurship competence development frameworks.

Table 1. Interpretation of *Al-Mu'minūn* (Chapter 23) Verses 1-4 by Haleem and Mawdūdī

Verse	Haleem (2016)	Mawdūdī (2009)
قَدْ أَفْلَحَ الْمُؤْمِنُونَ	[How] prosperous are the believers!	The believers have indeed attained true success
الَّذِينَ هُمْ فِي صَلَاتِهِمْ خَاشِعُونَ	Those who pray humbly	those who, in their Prayers, humble themselves;
وَالَّذِينَ هُمْ عَنِ اللَّغْوِ مُعْرِضُونَ	Who shun frivolity	who avoid whatever is vain and frivolous;
وَالَّذِينَ هُمْ لِلزَّكَاةِ فَاعِلُونَ	Who pay the prescribed alms	who observe Zakah;

By integrating classical exegesis, theological reasoning, and contemporary interpretations, this study develops a comprehensive understanding of Qur'ānic success. The traits and mental states identified in *al-Mu'minūn*—humility, focus, discipline, generosity, and ethical integrity—serve as foundation for both spiritual and practical achievements. These mindsets are adapted to serve as the foundation for developing SMART leading indicators for the Muslimpreneurship Competence Development Framework (MCDF).

While these indicators align with the Qur'ānic vision of success by merging spiritual fulfillment with practical competence, their significance extends further. Attitudes such as humility and focus, are fundamental components of competence. Attitudes are as critical as knowledge and skills in achieving entrepreneurship competence attainment. The MCDF points out that competence is more than just the ability to perform certain task; it also highlights the importance of alignment between personal virtues with professional objectives. This alignment ensures that Muslimpreneurs are guided toward achieving holistic success that reflects Qur'ānic ideals and entrepreneurial effectiveness.

It is widely accepted among Qur'anic scholars that *al-Mu'minūn* was revealed in Makkah, a city known for its entrepreneurial vibrancy and wealth during that time. This chapter outlines fundamental attitudes that characterise successful and prosperous believers. These include humility, focus, discipline, generosity, and ethical integrity. These attitudes are deeply interconnected, not isolated from one another. For instance, focus—highlighted in verse 3 regarding the avoidance of *laghw* (frivolous talk)—guides purposeful action, while discipline ensures consistency in upholding values such as humility and generosity. Together, those traits and mental states form a complete foundation which are important for both spiritual growth and entrepreneurial accomplishment.

In business management, leading indicators are proactive measures that predict future success. The term *qad* in *Al-Mu'minūn* (23:1), translated as "Successful indeed are the believers,"

underscores certainty and assurance in the qualities required for success. Linguistically, *qad* signifies that success is not merely aspirational but a guaranteed outcome when key traits—such as humility, focus, discipline, and integrity—are exhibited.

From a management perspective, these traits are well aligned with leading indicators. They formed indicative behaviours and actions toward long-term objectives attainment. This proactive interpretation suggests that success is driven by cultivating these qualities as foundational competences rather than treating them as outcomes.

Based on Muslimpreneurship Competence Development Framework (MCDF), indicators like Islamic Spiritual Quotient (ISQ), productivity, and charitable growth serve as actionable, forward-looking metrics. These qualities reflect the function of *qad* in highlighting the certainty of success through deliberate and values-driven practice. It serves as a strategic, predictive method for entrepreneurship competence development and attainment.

The concept of humility (*khushu'*), described in *Al-Mu'minūn* (23:2) as a quality of successful believers, holds significant relevance for entrepreneurial success, particularly when framed within the context of business management. The verse emphasises humility in prayer, which reflects mental focus, self-discipline, and emotional regulation—core attributes of spiritual intelligence (SQ) that are equally critical in business and entrepreneurship.

In entrepreneurship domain, productivity and focus are critical drivers of success. The concept of avoiding frivolity—steering clear of non-essential, unproductive activities— as promoted in *Al-Mu'minun* (23:3) provides a practical framework for improving time management, communication, and strategic decision-making. This principle resonates with modern productivity strategies and entrepreneurial best practices which underlining the importance of having meaningful and purposeful actions. This teachings of avoiding frivolity integrates seamlessly into the areas of resource management competence, planning and management competence, as well as ethical and sustainable thinking competence.

The teaching of observing zakat, or the act of giving prescribed alms, offers a practical framework for integrating ethical principles and social responsibility into business management. Zakat aligns with contemporary practices such as corporate social responsibility (CSR) and sustainable resource management, The emphasize on the value of charitable actions, which require integrity and proactive efforts—qualities essential for successful entrepreneurship. Acting ethically and maintaining transparency are vital for building trust and ensuring sustainable business practices. These principles resonate with the foundations of Islamic economics and business ethics, which advocate for fairness, justice, and accountability in economic transactions (Beekun, 1996; Gamal, 2009).

By integrating the foundational principles from *al-Mu'minūn*, Muslimpreneurs can establish businesses that achieve success both in this world and in alignment with the spiritual goal of *al-falāh*—success in both temporal and eternal dimensions. These first four verses emphasis on focus, ethical behaviour, and disciplined time management. The teachings that are expected to directly enhance entrepreneurship competence. It also demonstrates the universal applicability of these Islamic teachings to modern business practices.

This approach is well aligned with the Islamisation of Knowledge movement, which aims to bridge Islamic principles and teachings with contemporary disciplines. One of its objectives is to create holistic and ethically sound frameworks. By incorporating values such as ethical conduct, focus, and self-discipline—concepts also highlighted in modern leadership theories by Goleman (2006) and Covey (1994)—this methodology effectively merges modern strategies for success with Islamic principles and teachings. This synthesis reflects the movement's vision to develop knowledge systems that address contemporary challenges faced by Muslims while preserving moral and spiritual integrity. Islamisation of Knowledge offers a balanced approach to personal and professional growth which is useful for Muslims in general and particularly for Muslim diaspora who lives in western society.

SMART Indicators Measuring Success in Muslim Diaspora Entrepreneurship

In light of these Qur'ānic principles and teachings above, the following three SMART leading indicators are proposed as measures of success for Muslimpreneur within the MCDF:

1. Islamic Spiritual Quotient (ISQ)
2. Enhanced Productivity
3. Growth in Charitable Contributions and Assets

The first indicator is the Islamic Spiritual Quotient (ISQ). This indicator would measure the level of spiritual awareness and alignment with Islamic principles and teachings. ISQ is not merely about religious obedience, but it can be utilised to measure how profoundly a Muslimpreneur integrates spiritual commitment into their professional life.

For Muslimpreneurs, ISQ includes: (a) The integration of faith into decision-making, demonstrating *khushu'* in their work by being mindful, intentional, and ethical. (b) Prioritising their spiritual obligations, such as consistent prayer, as a foundation for balance and focus on entrepreneurship. (c) Commitment to values such as honesty, justice, and accountability, which translate to trust-building and integrity in business practices.

In the MCDF, ISQ reflects the attainment of ethical and sustainable thinking competence, motivation and perseverance competence self-awareness and efficacy competence, as well as coping with ambiguity, uncertainty and risk competence.

The concept of Islamic Spiritual Quotient (ISQ) is developed based on the concept of Spiritual Intelligence (SI). This measurement aims to evaluate the spiritual awareness integration with practical intelligence to improve life outcomes and decision-making. In the Islamic context, ISQ is often grounded in Qur'ānic teachings and Prophetic traditions which emphasise the importance of Islamic values alignment with personal and ethical development (Rahman & Shah, 2015)

The concept of ISQ has been formed and developed by various scholars. They combined Islamic philosophy with modern psychological frameworks. One example is the Emotional Spiritual Quotient (ESQ) model which is introduced by Ary Ginanjar Agustian. This indicator measures the integration the tenets of Iman, Islam, and Ihsan into a framework. It is developed to

nurture emotional and spiritual growth, particularly in leadership and organisational settings (Janah et al., 2021)

Scholars like Hanefar, Sa'ari, and Siraj (2016) have also conducted a study on the synthesis of spiritual intelligence. They compared Islamic and Western philosophical perspectives, highlighting unique Islamic dimensions such as *tawhīd* (unity of God), *adab* (ethics), and *taqwā* (God-consciousness). Their studies confirm that ISQ can be measured and applied through both qualitative and quantitative methods. Despite the tools is still evolving, these tools can be applied to evaluate aspects like spiritual well-being, moral decision-making, and alignment with Islamic principles

The reliability of specific ISQ measurement tools indeed depends on their methodological rigour and the contexts in which they are applied. Fortunately, these ISQ measurement tools are becoming increasingly recognised in academic and practical fields. However, many argue that more validation is needed to standardize ISQ assessments across diverse Muslim populations, especially for application in entrepreneurial and diaspora contexts.

The second leading indicator focuses on enhanced productivity, not merely in economic terms, but as a reflection of the believer's commitment to fulfilling their role in the world as described in the Qur'ān. As a leading indicator, measuring productivity means to determine how much effective time dedicated to managing resource. The productive activities should be motivated by an ethical responsibility to serve God through society. This indicator is aligned with the Qur'anic command to avoid futility and be purposeful in one's actions.

The principle of avoiding frivolity (*laghw*) in *al-Mu'minūn* 23:3 highlights the importance of purposeful action and time management. Enhanced productivity within the MCDF should surpass traditional economic metrics. It should reflect how the Muslimpreneurs manage its valuable resource, time as their accountability toward the ultimate resource owner. Ensuring the pleasure of the true resource owner by making meaningful contributions to the communities while avoiding things that displease Him, the futilities.

Key aspects of this indicator include: (a) Effective time management; this indicator ensures that the conducted activities are aligned with both spiritual and entrepreneurial objectives. (b) Ethical resource utilisation; this indicator is driven by a mindset of stewardship and accountability, as emphasized in the Qur'ān. (c) Demonstrating focus and intentionality in tasks, reflecting *khushu'* and a commitment to excellence.

There isn't a tool uniquely branded for Islamic entrepreneurship. For this purpose, the application of tools like Mohammed Faris's Productive Muslim framework (Faris, 2017) alongside standard SMART goal setting can be applied to facilitate Muslimpreneur maintain productivity while adhering to Islamic values. Faris (2017) proposes a framework of KPIs to assess spiritual, physical, and social productivity. These KPIs would measure time spent on various activities, encouraging productive Muslims to dedicate their time for personal growth, social influence, and spiritual practices. This tool emphasizes the importance of prioritising tasks and aligning them with long-term goals and vision as a Muslim.

The third leading indicator is related to increased charitable assets and contributions, a fundamental aspect of Islamic entrepreneurial ethics. This indicator measures how an entrepreneur contributes to the welfare of others and supports the common good (*maslaha*). Charitable actions, such as the payment of zakat (obligatory alms) and investment in community projects, can serve as both a spiritual act and a social responsibility. This indicator directly aligns with ESG reporting practices under the social and governance dimensions, where corporate giving, social welfare contributions and ethical impact are increasingly important benchmarks for long-term sustainability and trust of stakeholders (Wang, 2024).

Growth in charitable contributions and assets reflects a Muslimpreneur's ability to: (a) Treat wealth as a trust (*amanah*), recognising that resources must benefit society, as guided by Islamic ethics. (b) Actively support societal welfare through *zakat*, *sadaqah* (voluntary charity), and community investments, demonstrating both spiritual and social responsibility. (c) Build wealth with the intent of fostering economic justice and addressing inequalities, ensuring that business success uplifts others.

Tracking charitable contributions as a percentage of revenue and monitoring their social impact (e.g., the number of beneficiaries) can be quantifiable metrics. A diaspora business could use this indicator to strengthen community ties and enhance its socio-economic contributions.

Currently, there are no widely recognised *SMART tools* specifically designed to measure the growth in charitable assets and contributions for Islamic entrepreneurship or religiously aligned organisations. However, some general tools and approaches from the nonprofit and charitable sectors can be adapted.

CONCLUSION

The introduction of these three SMART leading indicators, especially growth in charitable asset and contribution represents significant evolution in the MCDF. By applying concrete and measurable indicators to the process of entrepreneurship competence development, the MCDF would become a more practical and actionable tool for Muslimpreneurs. The indicators would provide a roadmap for both personal and professional growth that in accordance with Islamic principles and teachings. Entrepreneurial activities then do not become just the pursuit of profit but also as a mean for ethics and spiritual fulfillment.

These SMART indicators would give Muslimpreneurs, especially those in the diaspora, a clear framework for achieving success that meets both Qur'anic ideals and globally recognised ESG benchmarks. These tracking tool enables faith and business practices integration. By highlighting the zakat and charity as one of the leading indicators, this framework enables a meaningful fusion of faith-driven practice and social responsibility, reinforcing the role of Muslim entrepreneurship in promoting ethical success and lasting social impact within the Islamic social economy. The diaspora Muslimpreneurs then can not only contribute to the global economy but also fulfill its main duty to serve God. Their competence development and successful entrepreneurship achievement will be well aligned with Islamic principles and teachings.

REFERENCES

- Ali, J. A. (2012). Contemporary Islamic Revivalism: Key Perspective. *The American Journal of Islamic Social Sciences*, 29(1), 60–97. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rel13090821>
- Ali, J. A. (2020). Part 1: Muslim settlement, immigration, and the emergence of Islam in Australia. In *Islam and Muslims in Australia: Settlement, Integration, Shariah, Education and Terrorism* (pp. 9–27). Melbourne University Press.
- Azhar, R. M. (2024). The Application of Islamic Principles on Entrepreneurship Competence Development Framework. *Australian Journal of Islamic Studies*, 9(1), 55–85. <https://doi.org/10.55831/ajis.v9i1.583>
- Bacigalupo, M., Kamyli, P., Punie, Y., Van den Brande, G., & European Commission, Joint Research Centre. (2016). *EntreComp: The entrepreneurship competence framework*. Publications Office of the European Union. <https://doi.org/10.2791/160811>
- Basu, A., & Altinay, E. (2002). The Interaction between Culture and Entrepreneurship in London's Immigrant Businesses. *International Small Business Journal: Researching Entrepreneurship*, 20(4), 371–393. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0266242602204001>
- Beekun, R. I. (1996). *Islamic Business Ethics*. International Institute of Islamic Thought. <https://doi.org/10.55849/solj.v1i3.487>
- Covey, S. R. (1994). *7 Habits of Highly Effective People: Restoring the Character Ethic*. RosettaBooks. <http://ebookcentral.proquest.com/lib/csuaa/detail.action?docID=3031863>
- Faris, M. (2017). *The Productive Muslim: Where Faith Meets Productivity (Fourth)*. Claritas Books.
- Fleischmann, F., & Phalet, K. (2018). Religion and National Identification in Europe: Comparing Muslim Youth in Belgium, England, Germany, the Netherlands, and Sweden. *Journal of Cross-Cultural Psychology*, 49(1), 44–61. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0022022117741988>
- Gamal, Mahmoud A. El-. (2009). Jurisprudence and arbitration. In *Islamic finance: Law, economics, and practice* (pp. 26–45). Cambridge University Press.
- Ghoul, W. A. (2017). Ethnic and migrant entrepreneurship: The case of Muslim Lebanese entrepreneurs in Dearborn. In V. Ramadani, L. P. Dana, S. Gërguri-Rashiti, & V. Ratten (Eds.), *Entrepreneurship and management in an Islamic context* (pp. 81-98). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-39679-8_6
- Goleman, D. (2006). *Emotional Intelligence (10th ed.)*. Bantam Books.
- Haleem, M. A. S. (2016). *The Quran*. Oxford University Press.
- Hanefar, S. B., Sa'ari, C. Z., & Siraj, S. (2016). A Synthesis of Spiritual Intelligence Themes from Islamic and Western Philosophical Perspectives. *Journal of Religion and Health*, 55(6), 2069–2085. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10943-016-0226-7>
- Iner, D., & Cufurovic, M. (2022). Moving beyond Binary Discourses: Islamic Universalism from an Islamic Revivalist Movement's Point of View. *Religions*, 13(9), 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rel13090821>

- Jakubowicz, A., Collins, J., Reid, C., & Chafic, W. (2014). Minority youth and social transformation in Australia: Identities, belonging and cultural capital. *Social Inclusion*, 2(2), 5–16. <https://doi.org/10.17645/SI.V2I2.162>
- Janah, E. N., Ritongah, I., & Nurhayati, N. (2021). Optimization of Superior ESQ and HR on the Preparation of Demographic Bonus in the Era of the Industrial Revolution 4.0. *Dinar: Jurnal Ekonomi Dan Keuangan Islam*, 8(2), 15–23. <https://doi.org/10.21107/dinar.v8i2.11026>
- Kramer, S., & Tong, Y. (2024). The Religious Composition of the World's Migrants. <https://www.pewresearch.org/religion/2024/08/19/muslim-migrants-around-the-world>
- Manzūr, M. ibn M. ibn A. ibn A. ibn. (1990). *Lisān al-‘Arab*. Dar al-Sadr.
- Mawdūdī, A. A. A.-. (2009). *Towards Understanding the Quran - Quran Translation Commentary - Tafheem ul Quran* (Z. I. Ansari, Ed.). The Islamic Foundation. <http://www.islamicstudies.info/tafheem.php?sura=103&verse=1&to=3>
- Olaofe, M. (2023). Entrepreneurship and Business Ethics from Islamic Perspective. *The International Journal of Humanities & Social Studies*, 11(1), 64–70. <https://doi.org/10.24940/theijhss/2023/v11/i1/HS2301-019>
- Rahman, Z. A., & Shah, I. M. (2015). Measuring Islamic Spiritual Intelligence. *Procedia Economics and Finance*, 31, 134–139. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2212-5671\(15\)01140-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2212-5671(15)01140-5)
- Roose, J. M., Peucker, M., & Akbarzadeh, S. (2023). Socio-Economic Disadvantages and Lack of Recognition: Impacts on Citizenship Within Australian Muslim Communities. *Journal of Intercultural Studies*, 44(2), 216–238. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07256868.2022.2102597>
- The Globalist. (2024). Muslims: A Global Perspective. In S. Richter (Ed.), *Just the Facts*. <https://www.theglobalist.com/muslims-islam-religion-arabic-population/>
- Wang, C. (2024). The relationship between ESG performance and corporate performance—Based on stakeholder theory. *SHS Web of Conferences*, 190, 03022. <https://doi.org/10.1051/shsconf/202419003022>
- Yilmaz, I. (2019). Muslim, Sacred Texts, and Laws in Modern World. In *Handbook of Contemporary Islam and Muslim Lives* (Vol. 1, Issue January 2019, pp. 2–18). <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-32626-5>